

(CASE REPORT)

A rare presentation of biclonal gammopathy in primary mediastinal lymph node plasmacytoma: A case report

Yousra El Amrani ^{1,2}, Btissam Ait Boucetta ^{1,2}, Imane El Khannouri ^{1,2}, Saliha Chellak ^{1,2} and Abderrahmane Boukhira ^{1,2}

¹ *Laboratory of Biochemistry and Toxicology, Avicenna Military Hospital, Marrakesh, Morocco.*

² *Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy of Marrakech. University Cadi Ayyad Marrakesh, Morocco.*

GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2024, 29(02), 299–303

Publication history: Received on 04 October 2024; revised on 18 November 2024; accepted on 21 November 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2024.29.2.0439>

Abstract

Primary plasmacytomas are localized proliferations of clonal plasma cells occurring in the absence of a systemic plasma cell dyscrasia, such as multiple myeloma. They most commonly manifest as solitary lesions in the bone or in the upper aerodigestive tract. Presentation in a lymph node is quite rare, especially when it involves the mediastinum. We report the case of a 32-year-old woman presenting with worsening dyspnea, cough, and chest discomfort, with radiologic evidence of mediastinal enlargement. An excisional biopsy of a large mediastinal mass revealed a plasma cell infiltrate, while protein electrophoresis analysis showed a biclonal gammopathy of the IgG kappa and IgA lambda type. She was treated with a myeloma-like regimen consisting of four cycles of bortezomib/dexamethasone followed by two cycles of thalidomide/prednisone, resulting in improvement of symptoms and complete resolution of lymphadenopathy. She remained in remission over 18 months following completion of therapy. This case report illustrates an unusual instance of biclonal gammopathy in primary mediastinal lymph node plasmacytoma, emphasizing its unique presentation and successful treatment through systemic therapy.

Keywords: Primary plasmacytoma; Mediastinal lymph node; Biclonal gammopathy; Plasma cell; Paraproteinemia

1. Introduction

Plasma cell neoplasms are characterized by the proliferation of malignant plasma cell clones, with multiple myeloma being the most prevalent form. This condition is marked by a significant presence of clonal plasma cells (>10%) in the bone marrow, alongside the detection of monoclonal proteins in serum and/or urine, and systemic symptoms CRAB (hypercalcemia, renal insufficiency, anemia, and bone lesions) [1, 2]. Notably, metastasis to lymph nodes occurs in approximately 40% of advanced-stage multiple myeloma cases [3]. In contrast, plasmacytomas represent local clonal proliferations of plasma cells without systemic involvement or bone marrow infiltration [4]. The most common presentation of primary plasmacytoma is solitary osseous plasmacytoma, where a singular bone lesion is observed [2]. Extramedullary plasmacytomas, occurring outside the bone, account for only 1.6% to 4% of all plasma cell tumors [5–7]. These extramedullary manifestations can arise in various organs but predominantly affect the upper respiratory tract, including the nasal cavity, sinuses, oropharynx, salivary glands, and larynx, which collectively represent 80% of reported cases. Other affected areas include the gastrointestinal tract, urogenital tract, skin, and lungs [5, 6]. Among these, primary lymph node plasmacytoma is exceptionally rare, representing only 2% of all extramedullary plasmacytomas [7], 0.5% of all malignant lymph node neoplasms [8], and a mere 0.08% of all plasma cell malignant neoplasms [7, 9]. At diagnosis, approximately 25% of patients with extramedullary plasmacytomas present monoclonal gammopathy [10]. The monoclonal protein is detected by serum protein electrophoresis as a single M-band most often in the gamma globulin region. In rare instances, 2–6% of cases may present with two distinct bands, which can result from either a single clone producing different types of immunoglobulins or the existence of two separate malignant

* Corresponding author: Y. EL AMRANI

Figure 2 Serum immunoelectrophoresis confirmed the presence of two monoclonal bands identified as IgA/Lambda and IgG/Kappa

A bone marrow biopsy performed shortly afterward demonstrated largely unremarkable trilineage hematopoiesis with 8% of plasma cells detected. Treatment was promptly initiated with subcutaneously administered bortezomib at a dose of 1.5 mg/m² and orally administered dexamethasone at 40 mg weekly for three weeks, followed by a one-week break. Following the initiation of this treatment, the patient experienced considerable improvement in platelet count and anemia, which allowed for the addition of thalidomide to her regimen. She completed four cycles of bortezomib/dexamethasone, after which she transitioned to two continuous 28-day cycles of thalidomide at a dose of 100 mg orally, administered alongside prednisone. The patient has maintained sustained remission for over 18 months following the completion of therapy, indicating a favorable response to treatment.

3. Discussion

Primary plasmacytomas can be categorized into two main types: medullary plasmacytoma, which originates in the bone marrow, and extramedullary plasmacytoma, typically found in soft tissues across various organs. These solid tumors predominantly occur in the upper respiratory tract, affecting areas such as the nasal cavity, sinuses, oropharynx, salivary glands, and larynx, accounting for about 80% of reported cases. They can also be found in the gastrointestinal and urogenital regions, as well as in the skin and lungs. [12]. Most plasmacytomas in lymph nodes are considered metastatic, stemming from multiple myeloma or other extramedullary plasmacytomas. Primary lymph node plasmacytomas are quite uncommon, representing only 2% of all extramedullary cases [7] and a mere 0.08% of all malignant plasma cell tumors [7, 9]. The current case is noteworthy due to its substantial size, involvement of the mediastinum, pleural effusion, and the presence of biclonal gammopathy. The exact reason for the pleural effusion remains uncertain, but it may be due to the tumor obstructing normal pulmonary lymphatic flow [13].

Primary plasmacytomas are defined as localized tumors without systemic manifestations of plasma cell malignancy. For a diagnosis of primary plasmacytoma of the lymph nodes, it is crucial to demonstrate the absence of plasma cell proliferation in other sites and to rule out any associated malignant lymphoma components [14].

Biclonal gammopathies are a vanishingly rare group characterized by the production of two distinct monoclonal proteins. This rare presentation can result from either a proliferation of two clones of plasma cells with each producing an unrelated monoclonal spike or from the production of two monoclonal spikes by a single clone of plasma cells. Approximately 1.5% of multiple myeloma cases present biclonal paraproteinemia [15]. Mullikin et al. [16] reported that

23 out of 393 patients with biclonal gammopathy of unknown significance in their study had progression to either multiple myeloma, smoldering myeloma, light chain amyloidosis or Waldenstrom macroglobulinemia with the dominant clone being the principal player through the course of the disease in 21 patients [16]. Several cases of isotype switching have been reported in myeloma patients with biclonal spikes. A case exhibited a shift from primarily IgG with a minor IgD component to a predominant IgD immunoglobulin production after chemotherapy with findings revealing neoplastic origin from a single clone of B-cells [17]. Franck et al. [18] reported another case with shift from a single paraprotein IgG Kappa to a biclonal paraprotein IgG kappa and IgD kappa. Pragnan et al. [10] reported the first case with biclonal gammopathy in multiple myeloma with simultaneous extramedullary involvement showing a presentation with lambda restricted IgG predominant cells from cervical lymph node and kappa restricted IgA cells from the bone marrow simultaneously. [10]

Because primary plasmacytomas are local phenomena, they may be treated and cured with local interventions. The mainstay of treatment is surgery and has a good prognosis. Extramedullary plasmacytoma is radiosensitive and is treated with radiotherapy [19]. In contrast, because multiple myeloma is a systemic disorder, it requires systemic treatments such as chemotherapy and/or immune therapy or autologous hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. Due to the extreme paucity of data describing systemic therapy for primary plasmacytoma, treatment had to be planned largely without well-established precedent. Given the anatomically diffuse nature of the disease, it was deemed prudent to pursue a myeloma-like regimen. [20] In our case, the massive mediastinal lymph node was diffused enough to make radiotherapy not feasible. Therefore, systemic therapy was deployed and the patient was treated with myeloma specific regimen VTD. Kyle et al. [15] reported no difference in prognosis between biclonal and monoclonal gammopathy. However, recognition of this existence increases the credibility and helps in assessing treatment response during follow-up.

4. Conclusion

This case report and accompanying literature review highlight the easily misclassified entity of primary extensive lymph-node plasmacytomas involving the mediastinum, potentially mistaken as lymphoid malignancy, and the exceedingly rare biclonal gammopathy that can have its origin from either a single clone or two clones of plasma cells. The recognizing and understanding of biclonal gammopathy in the context of plasmacytomas enables a precise diagnosis, an adequate treatment and an adjusted follow up response that takes into account the risk of future progression to systemic myeloma, particularly in cases with evidence of marrow involvement. Further research into the implications of biclonality in plasma cell neoplasms could provide valuable insights into patient management and therapeutic outcomes.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

We declare that the present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors. This case report is based on clinical observations and does not involve experimental interventions. It adheres to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki.

Statement of informed consent

We affirm that this case report complies with ethical standards for medical and academic publishing. The patient, an adult, provided written informed consent for the publication of the case details. All identifiable personal information has been anonymized to protect confidentiality.

References

- [1] Rajkumar SV, Kumar S. Multiple Myeloma: Diagnosis and Treatment. *Mayo Clin Proc.* 2016;91(1):101–19. doi: 10.1016/j.mayocp.2015.11.007

- [2] Dores GM, Landgren O, McGlynn KA, Curtis RE, Linet MS, Devesa SS. Plasmacytoma of bone, extramedullary plasmacytoma, and multiple myeloma: incidence and survival in the United States, 1992-2004. *Br J Haematol.* 2009;144(1):86–94. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2141.2008.07421.x
- [3] Wiltshaw E. The natural history of extramedullary plasmacytoma and its relation to solitary myeloma of bone and myelomatosis. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 1976; 55:217-238. doi: 10.1097/00005792-197605000-00002
- [4] Tohda S. Overview of lymphoid neoplasms in the fourth edition of the WHO classification. *Rinsho Byori.* 2012;60(6):560–4. PMID: 22880234
- [5] International Myeloma Working G. Criteria for the classification of monoclonal gammopathies, multiple myeloma and related disorders: a report of the International Myeloma Working Group. *Br J Haematol.* 2003; 121(5):749–57. PMID: 12780789
- [6] Gerry D, Lentsch EJ. Epidemiologic evidence of superior outcomes for extramedullary plasmacytoma of the head and neck. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2013 Jun;148(6):974–81. doi: 10.1177/0194599813481334.
- [7] Galieni P, Cavo M, Pulsoni A, Avvisati G, Bigazzi C, Neri S, Caliceti U, Benni M, Ronconi S, Lauria F. Clinical outcome of extramedullary plasmacytoma. *Haematologica.* 2000;85:47–51. doi: 10.1093/oxfordjournals.annonc.a059285.
- [8] Lennert K, Mohri N. Histopathology and diagnosis of nonHodgkin's lymphomas. In: Lennert K, ed. *Malignant Lymphomas Other Than Hodgkin's Disease: Histology, Cytology, Ultrastructure, Immunology.* New York, NY: Springer-Verlag; 1978:263-278.
- [9] Woodruff RK, Whittle JM, Malpas JS. Solitary plasmacytoma, I: extramedullary soft tissue plasmacytoma. *Cancer.* 1979 Jun;43(6):2340-3. doi: 10.1002/1097-0142(197906)43:6<2340::aid-cnrcr2820430625>3.0.co;2-m.
- [10] Pragnan Kancharla; Eshan Patel, Kenneth Hennrick, Sherif Ibrahim, Mendel Goldfinger. A Rare Presentation of Biclonal Gammopathy in Multiple Myeloma with Simultaneous Extramedullary Involvement: case rep oncol. 2019 Jul 16;12(2):537-542. doi: 10.1159/000499902.
- [11] Srinivasan VK, Bhagat P, Bansal F, Chhabra S. Occurrence of double monoclonal bands on protein electrophoresis: an unusual finding. *Indian J Hematol Blood Transfus.* 2016 Jun;32 (S1Suppl 1):184–8. doi: 10.1007/s12288-015-0622-2
- [12] Lee SY, Kim JH, Shin JS, et al. A case of extramedullary plasmacytoma arising from the posterior mediastinum. *Korean J Intern Med.* 2005,20(2);173–6. doi: 10.3904/kjim.2005.20.2.173
- [13] Scullin DC Jr, Cohen HJ. Myelomatous pleural effusion: Clinical course and immunological characterization of the pleural fluid cells. *Am J Hematol.* 1979;6(3):267-73. doi: 10.1002/ajh.2830060311.
- [14] Naymagon L, Abdul-Hay Primary extramedullary plasmacytoma with diffuse lymph node involvement: a case report and review of the literature. *M. J Med Case Rep.* 2019 May 22;13(1):153. doi: 10.1186/s13256-019-2087-7.
- [15] Kyle RA, Robinson RA, Katzmann JA. The clinical aspects of biclonal gammopathies. Review of 57 cases. *Am J Med.* 1981 Dec;71(6):999–1008. doi: 10.1016/0002-9343(81)90326-0
- [16] Mullikin TC, Rajkumar SV, Dispenzieri A, Buadi FK, Lacy MQ, Lin Y, et al. Clinical characteristics and outcomes in biclonal gammopathies. *Am J Hematol.* 2016 May;91(5):473–5. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajh.24319>[PubMed] 0361-8609
- [17] Gallart T, Bladé J, Martínez-Quesada J, Sierra J, Rozman C, Vives J. Multiple myeloma with monoclonal IgG and IgD of lambda type exhibiting, under treatment, a shift from mainly IgG to mainly IgD. *Immunology.* 1985 May;55(1):45–57. PMID: 3922877
- [18] Franck P, Petitpain N, Guerci AP, Denisart S, Jacob C, Guéant JL. Myeloma with two monoclonal IgG and IgD in serum: a case report. *Acta Haematol.* 1994;92(3):144–7. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000204206>[PubMed] 0001-5792
- [19] Young Hyo Lim, Su Kyoung Park, Ho Suk Oh, Jung Hye Choi, Myung Ju Ahn, Young Yul Lee, In Soon Kim. A Case of Primary Plasmacytoma of Lymph Nodes. *Korean J Intern Med.* 2005 Jun 30;20 (2):183–186. doi: 10.3904/kjim.2005.20.2.183
- [20] Alfar R, Al-Shatti M, Alomari Z, Bater R, Rahal R, Abdel-Razeq R, Sharaf B (2022) Primary Extra-Medullary Plasmacytoma with Diffuse Lymph Node Involvement, Lymphoma Diagnostic Mimicry: A Case Report and Review of the Literature. *Med Case Rep Vol.8 No.6:230* doi: 10.36648/2471-8041.8.6.230